

Scientific article

Experimental Investigation of the Inflow Turbulence Intensity Effect on the Helix Wake Mixing Technique

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Abstract: *We present an experimental investigation of the influence of inflow turbulence intensity on the effectiveness of the Helix wake mixing control strategy. Wind tunnel experiments were conducted using two in-line wind turbine models under low ($TI \approx 1.5\%$) and high ($TI \approx 6\%$) turbulence conditions. Power measurements and Particle Tracking Velocimetry were employed to assess wake recovery and downstream turbine performance. Results show that higher ambient turbulence accelerates natural wake recovery, while Helix control provides substantial additional benefits under low turbulence inflow. Under high turbulence conditions, Helix remains beneficial but with reduced effectiveness.*

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